

Some Entropy Based on Measurement Distribution and Not Physical System?

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Shannon's entropy is calculated using probabilities $P(i)$ i.e. $S = - \sum_i P(i) \ln(P(i))$. A probability is related to an uncertainty associated with event i , but this event may not be a physical event, but rather a measurement. In other words, measurements in a system may be made according to one distribution or another. This distribution may be converted into something which looks like a probability even though the system is completely deterministic. The entropy then calculated is based on the measurement distribution and not the physical system.

As a first example, consider the completely deterministic motion of a bound classical system between two turning points. Person A may send values of x (one dimensional space) to person B, based on a certain distribution instead of sending the values based on time i.e. $x(t_1), x(t_2)$ etc. One distribution which may be used is the uniform one i.e. $P(x) = dx/L$. Another distribution, used in the literature (1), is based on the time spent in each constant dx i.e. $P(x) = Cdx/v(x)$ where $v(x)$ is velocity. These two distributions lead to different Shannon's entropies, but the underlying system is completely deterministic which begs the question: Why does one associate an entropy with it? The entropy seems to be associated with the sending of information.

We try to apply these ideas to a quantum bound state. In the literature (2), one sometimes sees a Shannon's entropy based on $W(x)W(x) = P(x)$, where $W(x)$ is the single particle bound wavefunction. This is a distribution, but is it based on uncertainty in the system? $W(x)W(x)$ often consists of a set of crests of different heights and widths. We argue that the inherent uncertainty in x is due to the width of a crest. In other words each crest may be normalized to 1 and a Shannon's entropy for each crest calculated. One must then weight the different crests. If one calculates the classical time associated with the base length of crest, this could be used as a weight which in the high energy level limit is associated with $P(x) = Cdx/v(x)$ from (1), but it seems there is no reason to base the weight on time. The uncertainty in x is due to a superposition of $\exp(ipx)$ s which are not linked to time. Alternatively, one may use an unnormalized weight of the length of the base as uncertainty is only in x . One may then add a Shannon's momentum entropy using $a(p)a(p) = P(p)$ where $W(x) = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$.

Entropy Based on Measurement Distribution

Shannon's entropy is given by:

$$S = - \sum_i P(i) \ln(P(i)) \quad ((1))$$

where $P(i)$ is a probability for event i . This suggests an intrinsic uncertainty in a physical system, but we argue that alternatively, one may associate a distribution with a deterministic system and deliver measurements in accordance with the distribution. In such a case, probabilities are based on the measurement distribution, not the physical system, and the resulting entropy reflects this.

As an example, consider a classical bound particle moving in one dimension between two turning points. This situation is completely deterministic and so it is not clear why there should be an associated entropy.

Imagine that Person A measures a set of x values associated with the system according to a certain distribution and sends them to Person B. One approach is for person A to send x values corresponding to successive times i.e. $x(t_0), x(t_1), x(t_2)$ etc with $t_1=t_0+\Delta t, t_2=t_1+\Delta t$ etc. This shows the deterministic nature of the problem. Person A, however, may send x data in any way he/she wishes i.e. according to different distributions. For example, Person A may use a uniform distribution. In such a case, $P(x) = dx/L$ where L is the distance between turning points. Person B may notice this distribution and create $P(x)$ and also a corresponding Shannon's entropy, but it has nothing to do with the deterministic bound state motion.

Alternatively, Person A may choose x values based on a probability proportional to dt , i.e. the time spent by the particle in a fixed dx length. In such a case, $P(x) = C dx/v(x)$ where $.5mv(x)^2 + V(x) = E$. Again, there is no reason for this probability and its Shannon's entropy to characterize the classical deterministic system. Such an entropy is used in (1) as it is said to represent the high energy level spatial entropy of a quantum bound state. We thus consider such a state.

Quantum Bound State

A quantum bound state is based on a wavefunction $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ which satisfies the time-independent Schrodinger equation:

$$-1/2m \frac{d^2 W}{dx^2} + V(x) = E_n \quad ((2))$$

$P(x) = W(x)W(x)$ in quantum mechanics, but we argue that this is a distribution. The real uncertainty, we suggest, is in $\exp(ipx)$ i.e. a constant p has $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ humps. There is uncertainty with a $\cos(px)$ hump to find the particle within half a wavelength. $W(x)$ itself is composed of crests and troughs so that $W(x)W(x)$ consists of humps of different heights and widths, but these are partly associated with deterministic average classical behaviour i.e.

$$KE(x)_{\text{classical}} = -1/2m \frac{d^2 W}{dx^2} \quad ((3))$$

Thus $W(x)W(x)$ is a distribution and using it as a probability in Shannon's entropy (as done in (2) etc) does not necessarily capture uncertainty in the system. We suggest that the uncertainty is represented by each crest. In other words, if one normalizes each crest separately then:

$$P(x)_{\text{within a crest}} = W(x)W(x) C_1 \quad (x \text{ within a crest}) \quad ((4)) \quad C_1 = \text{normalization constant}$$

Using this $P(x)$, one may create a Shannon's entropy for each normalized crest.

The question is then: How does one combine these crest entropies? One may suggest a weighted average. One approach is to use a weight based on the time a classical particle spends traversing the base length of the crest. In the high energy level limit this approximates

the $Cdx/v(x)$ probability. Physically, however, it seems there is no reason to use time weights. A crest in $W(x)W(x)$ is already based on the uncertainties of $\exp(ipx)$ s combining so that $KE(x) = -1/2m d/dx dW/dx$. It seems that the base of a hump indicates a region in which there is uncertainty in x . Thus we suggest using the length of the base as a weight i.e.

$$\text{Spatial entropy} = \text{Sum over crests } i \quad S(i) \{ \text{Base length of crest } i \} \quad ((5))$$

where $S(i)$ is the Shannon's entropy created using the probability in ((4)).

Momentum Considerations

Momentum considerations also exist because there is a probability $a(p)a(p)$ to have momentum p at each x , where $W(x) = \text{sum over } p \quad a(p)\exp(ipx)$. We suggest one may add to ((5)) a momentum entropy:

$$S(\text{momentum}) = - \text{Sum over } p \quad a(p)a(p) \ln\{a(p)a(p)\} \quad ((6))$$

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that a Shannon's entropy is based on a set of probabilities $P(i)$ for event i , but i may actually not correspond to any uncertainty in a system, but rather to a distribution associated with a set of measurements. For example, a classical bound system is completely deterministic. Person A may send x information (one dimensional space information) based on any kind of distribution. For example, a uniform distribution may be used, or one based on time spent in constant dx i.e. $P(x) = Cdx/v(x)$ ($v(x) = \text{velocity}$) (1). This, in turn, gives rise to entropies based on measurement distributions and not the physical system.

The probability $P(x) = Cdx/v(x)$ is used to estimate the high energy level quantum spatial entropy (1) and so we argue that $P(x) = W(x)W(x)$ is a distribution and does not necessarily capture spatial uncertainty in the single particle bound system. We suggest normalizing each crest in $W(x)W(x)$ separately and calculating a Shannon's entropy per crest as a way to try to capture uncertainty ultimately due to the uncertainty from $\exp(ipx)$ in x . One may then take a weighted average using the base length of a crest as its weight. Finally, one may add a momentum entropy $- \text{Sum over } p \quad a(p)a(p) \ln\{a(p)a(p)\}$.

References

1. Majernick, V. and Opatrny, T. Entropic Uncertainty relations for a Harmonic Oscillator
 January 1999 [Journal of Physics A Mathematical and General](#) 29(9):2187
 DOI: [10.1088/0305-4470/29/9/029](https://doi.org/10.1088/0305-4470/29/9/029)

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/231048623_Entropic_uncertainty_relations_for_a_quantum_oscillator

2. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Particle_in_a_box